

Fishbanks

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Keywords

Business, Climate-change Education, Collaborative Problem-solving, Strategic Decision-making, Sustainability, Systems Thinking, Tragedy of the Commons

Introduction

Fishbanks is a digital educational game, developed in 1992 by Dennis Meadows, John Sterman, and Andrew King in the Massachusetts Institute of Technology (MIT Sloan School of Management, n.d.). It simulates the socio-economic dynamics of the fishing industry. Players take on the role of fishermen and women who aim to maximize profits and minimize total costs. During the game, conflicts are staged in which players must act in their own interests and in society's interests. In this way, players encounter difficulties building trust and engaging in joint decision-making, and have to develop binding behavioral rules. Through the allocation of fixed fishing areas and fluctuations in fish stocks, players are forced to negotiate with each other about where and how much fishing is allowed. In the process, additional costs arise, for example, in the purchase and sale of fish and the construction of ships. Through auctions, permits, and quotas, players learn about the sustainable management of a shared body of water. They can thus improve their understanding of the interrelationships among the environment, the economy, and society.

Facts

Release date:	1992; online version released 2010
Developer:	Dennis Meadows, John Sterman, and Andrew King of the Massachusetts Institute of Technology
Game type:	Hybrid, digital & analog variants
Number of players:	Multiplayer
Format:	Synchronous
Time frame:	2–3 h
Languages:	The game is available in English, Spanish, Portuguese, and Chinese
Environment:	For digital play: access to computers
Material:	Guidelines for teachers
Price:	Online version free of charge; analogue versions currently cost \$185 (System Dynamics Society, 2025)

Resonance & Criticism

Figure 1. Photo of the Fishbanks game (MIT / Dennis Meadows et al.). Used for educational review. Rights remain with the creators.

With its first publication in the early 90s and the introduction of the digital version in 2010, Fishbanks remains one of the most well-known educational games (Ruiz-Pérez et al., 2011). As early as 2014, a study found that about 30% of participating academics had implemented the learning game in their professional or academic lives, and that the game already enjoyed great popularity in university contexts (Amaral & Hess, 2018). Over the years, numerous spin-offs of the original have been created, including modified and, in some cases, analogue game variants (Sherpa, n.d.), all of which have retained the basic principles of the traditional game.

Game Principle & Process

In Fishbanks, the team that can claim the highest profit at the end of the game wins. This sum is made up of the general capital of the groups and the value of the boats in their fleets. As in real life, profit is calculated here from the difference between income and expenses, which are determined by the sale of fish and boats or by harbor and operating costs. The various prices can be adjusted depending on the game variant: auctions can take place, taxes can be

waived, and loans can be taken out. Varying fish stocks and different water types create many opportunities for players to influence the game and become the best fishing company.

Based on the “tragedy of the commons”, a theory that describes the result of free trade among individuals who, out of self-interest, seek to maximize their personal benefit and do not consider the common good, Fishbanks simulates the economic effects of the competitive use of shared resources (Ruiz-Pérez et al., 2011). According to this theory, the possible long-term consequences of self-interested management are often ignored, so that the overexploitation and overloading of public resources ultimately harms the public (Barnett, 1982). To prevent this, public resources can either be privatised, or regulations that limit their use must be created and adhered to, which is another aspect that Fishbanks' game mechanisms try to stimulate.

Learning Objectives & Educational Fields of Application

Fishbanks' unique concept has made it one of the most widely used educational games, aligned with high school and university curricula. The competition-based game approach is suitable for economics, and its environmental and social focus also ensures a wide range of academic applications (Ruiz-Pérez et al., 2011). Since there are fewer fish available for everyone whenever a team catches one, the fishermen and women have to agree on rules and regulations, such as fishing quotas, to prevent an impending collapse of the ecosystem. As a result, not only are profit maximisation and economic success the central goals of the game, but social and societal aspects must be given equal consideration for the game to play out positively.

To support teachers in implementing the educational game in the classroom, various instructions and curricula can be found and used online (‘FishBanks Simulation Guide’, 2015). Before the original version of Fishbanks can be used in teaching units, teachers must apply for group codes on the game page and ensure that they have access to computers or other Internet-enabled devices. As a teacher, it is helpful to familiarize oneself with the game content in advance so that sufficient answers can be provided to players' questions. It is also helpful to ask students to write down their experiences before, after, and during the game. This way, the game's dynamics can be discussed in detail, and the entire gaming experience gains thematic depth. Finally, the outcomes of Fishbanks should be reflected on together, and players can, for example, start a second game with their own set of political guidelines or a stronger focus on the interactions between cause and effect.

Effectiveness

The economic, environmental, and societal aspects of Fishbanks' concept enable players to educate themselves across many fields effectively. A 2014 study at the Federal University of São Paulo showed that the educational game can increase players' general environmental awareness in a fun way (Amaral & Hess, 2018). In particular, learners are introduced to the

complex dynamics of managing common-pool resources by placing strong emphasis on ecological consequences and risks (Amaral & Hess, 2018). In the process, the learning game trains problem-solving skills and can actively improve the players' systemic thinking (Amaral & Hess, 2018).

Potentially Problematic Aspects

Fishbanks relies heavily on simplified economic and ecological assumptions. This abstraction can create a misleading sense of predictability in real-world resource management, where political, cultural, and historical factors play significant roles. Competitive gameplay may also overshadow collaborative learning, unintentionally reinforcing profit-maximization over sustainability. Finally, the simulation's emphasis on negotiation dynamics can disadvantage players who are less confident or less experienced with strategic communication, potentially affecting learning outcomes.

Reviewer(s): Johannes Katsarov

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